

TASKS OF INCREASING THE ECONOMIC EFFICIENCY OF INDUSTRIAL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract: Focusing on the further economic and social development of economic production analysis of market relations, determining the state of the judicial process. For this purpose, continuous development of economic analysis as a science, provision of its methodology, widespread implementation of analytical work of computers in practice, production requirements of other latest technical, economic, mathematical and other rational research methods of data collection and processing. economic processes.

Key words: Economic activity, resources, retrospective, production, economic optimization.

It helps to learn, generalize and increase the theoretical level of analysis of future economic activities.

Analysis of economic activity is one of the tools of economic management, and occupies an intermediate position between collection and management decision-making, that is, the analysis precedes management decisions and prepares them for justification. Effective and efficient management of businesses and economic entities requires knowledge of available resources and support, sustainability, and economic and social management. Such information is primarily an operational and current (retrospective) economic analysis utility. Through analysis, they identify and control problems to control the studied work of plans, economic and social dynamics, management, identify and produce work problems, if any. eliminate them and get them. At the same time, it focuses on production.

When planning the economic activity of enterprises, especially for the long term, it is difficult to take into account all the possibilities and reserves of economic improvement. Many of them are identified and used in the implementation of plans through in-depth economic analysis. Therefore, the analysis not only provides an impartial assessment of the implementation of plans and the dynamics of socio-economic development, but also helps to study and generalize best practices, to identify ways, opportunities and reserves to optimize the economy of enterprises. Thus, before drawing up plans, it is necessary to conduct a deep analysis of the economic activity of enterprises during the pre-planning period, which helps to justify the planned indicators and more fully reflect the available reserves in them. In the process of analysis, the quality of planning, interdependence

and consistency of planned indicators, available opportunities to improve management efficiency and the completeness of accounting in reserve plans are studied. All this helps to prepare optimal plans and forecasts that ensure high growth rates and optimal rates of development of certain aspects of the economic activity of enterprises. Economic analysis helps to observe the mode of saving in the use of material, labor and financial resources, to develop and strengthen self-sufficiency and self-financing. In the conditions of the market economy, there are unlimited opportunities to save living and material labor costs. Identifying these opportunities and making full use of them is one of the most important tasks of the analysis.

The importance of economic analysis in increasing the intensity of social production, introducing scientific and technical achievements into the practice of enterprises. With the help of preliminary analysis of economic activity, the appropriateness and efficiency of the introduced innovations are determined. Further analysis (operational and ongoing) will help to determine the impact of introduced technical progress, new technological advances.

Thus, with the help of economic analysis, the economic mechanism, planning, management are improved, economic accounting is introduced and developed. This is the most important tool for scientific forecasting of the prospects of business entities.

The tasks of analyzing economic activity arise from its nature, content, importance and socio-economic tactics and short- and long-term strategy of the enterprise. These tasks can be summarized as follows:

- checking the reality and optimality of plans, forecasts, standards, norms;
- to help improve the planning and management system;
- control of the implementation of plans, business plans, comprehensive and impartial assessment of all indicators; study and evaluation of development trends in the dynamics of the enterprise's economy, the conditions and methods of obtaining the results of economic activity;
- determination and quantitative measurement of the influence of factors on the indicators of economic activity of the enterprise; give an objective assessment of the results of one's work;
- studying the safety and effectiveness of the use of material (goods), labor and financial resources, natural resources; to support the introduction of scientific and technical development and advanced methods of management into the practice of the enterprise;
- development of measures to eliminate deficiencies and deficiencies identified during the analysis; study and mobilization of reserves to increase the efficiency of economic potential;
- making the right management decisions and supporting their successful implementation.

Further economic and social development of enterprises, transition to market relations, computerization of management puts new, more complex tasks before the science and practice of analysis of economic activity in order to optimize the activities of economic entities. The successful implementation of these tasks will contribute to the optimal development of the national economy and increase the material and cultural standard of living of the population.

The results of the work of enterprises, their structural divisions and business organizations depend on several factors of an economic, organizational, technical and technological nature.

In economic studies, the conditions of economic processes and the reasons affecting them are usually understood as factors. Business activities are complex and multifaceted. It is a set of interrelated economic processes characterized by a system of indicators depending on many and diverse factors. In-depth study of the set of factors affecting the execution of plans and the dynamics of management provides an opportunity to correctly assess the activities of enterprises, to identify and use reserves for the growth of their economic potential. efficiency of social production.

Each factor can consist of several reasons, which in turn act as independent factors that affect the results of economic, investment and financial activities of enterprises to a greater or lesser extent. Therefore, the factors can be of the first, second, third, ... n-order. The more detailed they are, the more detailed they are studied, the more fully available reserves are revealed to improve the economic activity of enterprises.

These factors are interrelated and often affect the results of economic and other activities of enterprises in different directions: some are positive, others are negative, and others are neutral in the current economic development conditions. In addition, the negative effects of some factors can reduce or eliminate the positive effects of others. All this requires the study of as many factors as possible.

In order to deeply study the influence of factors on the economic activity of the enterprise, it is necessary to give their scientifically based classification. First of all, it should be distinguished:

- production-economic factors, or necessary conditions for the implementation of economic activity. These include resource factors (labor tools, labor objects, and labor itself);
- technical and economic factors (mechanization and automation of production, trade and other technological processes, introduction of achievements in science, technology, advanced technology and labor organization);
- socio-economic factors reflecting the creative initiative and activity of workers (participation of workers in the management of the enterprise, initiative of producers, moral encouragement and interest of workers in the results of work), level of enterprise management;
- socio-psychological factors (collective relations, mutual responsibility and mutual assistance, conflict situations);
- physiological factors (sanitary-hygienic working conditions, improvement of production and labor organization, aesthetic condition of buildings, etc.).

According to the degree of influence on work results, the factors are divided into the following: main (identifier); small.

The main factors are the factors that have a decisive influence on the economic activity of the enterprise in the current conditions.

First you need to study their actions.

All other factors are secondary.

Factors are divided into measurable and non-quantifiable according to the degree of quantitative measurement of their influence on the effective indicator.

Quantitative measurement of the influence of factors on the studied indicator allows to correctly assess the economic activity of enterprises. If it is not possible to do this (for example, to measure the effect of seniority, general education and professional training of workers on their labor productivity), it is necessary to observe the direction of the influence of factors. This allows for more reasonable conclusions and recommendations based on the results of the economic analysis. According to the time of action, the factors are permanent, acting continuously during the studied period, and temporary, affecting for a certain period of time.

Factors are classified as intensive and extensive.

Intensive factors are related to scientific and technical progress, the most effective use of advanced technological achievements. They ensure the development of the economy by increasing social labor productivity, improving the use of material, labor, financial resources and natural resources.

Broad factors are related to the expansion of the material and technical base of the enterprise, additional involvement of material and labor resources, development of economic potential. The decisive factors at the current stage of development of our economy and in the future are the factors that ensure the growth of labor productivity and increase the efficiency of the use of economic resources. Special attention should be paid to these factors in the analysis. But the study of large-scale factors that ensure the development of the economy by attracting additional production and other resources cannot be neglected.

According to the scope of activity, the factors act in the entire national economy, in particular, in separate sectors of the economy or in individual enterprises.

General factors include the provision and use of material and labor resources, the material and technical base of enterprises, and specific factors - the location of individual enterprises, the contingent of consumers they serve.

According to the level of detail, the factors are divided into simple ones, which are the result of a single cause, and complex ones, which arise under the influence of a set of causes. Simple factors include the number of days in the analyzed period, and complex factors include the productivity of workers.

According to the movement detection method, the factors are direct, their effects are directly determined and calculated, their movement is determined by special techniques and is measured using calculations.

Factors affecting the results of economic activity can be positive and negative. Studying the factors that have a positive effect on the results of economic activity allows more accurate identification of reserves to increase economic potential and improve its use. successful implementation of plans and sustainable economic development. Analysis of the factors that have a negative impact prevents their occurrence, helps to eliminate the shortcomings in the work.

According to the essence of the action, the factors are divided depending on the employees of the enterprise and their work results, which are not related to the activities of the enterprises.

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